

Genetic Algorithms Based Parameter Optimization for Disparity Map Generation of Radiata Pine Branch Images

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Abstract—Traditional stereo matching algorithms like Semi-Global Block Matching (SGBM) with Weighted Least Squares (WLS) filtering offer speed advantages over neural networks for UAV applications, generating disparity maps in approximately 0.5 seconds per frame. However, these algorithms require meticulous parameter tuning. We propose a Genetic Algorithm (GA) based parameter optimization framework that systematically searches for optimal parameter configurations for SGBM and WLS, enabling UAVs to measure distances to tree branches with enhanced precision while maintaining processing efficiency. Our contributions include: (1) a novel GA-based parameter optimization framework that eliminates manual tuning; (2) a comprehensive evaluation methodology using multiple image quality metrics; and (3) a practical solution for resource-constrained UAV systems. Experimental results demonstrate our GA-optimized approach reduces Mean Squared Error by 42.86% while increasing Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio and Structural Similarity by 8.47% and 28.52%, respectively, compared to baseline configurations. Furthermore, our approach demonstrates superior generalization performance across varied imaging conditions, which is critical for real-world forestry applications.

Index Terms—Genetic Algorithm, Stereo Vision, Tree Pruning, Drone.

I. INTRODUCTION

The timber industry represents a significant component of New Zealand's economy, with Radiata Pine being a predominant commercial species across the country's plantation forests [1]. Regular pruning of Radiata Pine is essential for enhancing wood quality, promoting straight trunk growth, and accelerating timber production. Traditionally, this pruning process requires workers to physically climb trees, which presents substantial safety hazards due to the considerable heights involved and, in some locations, proximity to high-voltage power lines. To address these safety concerns and increase operational efficiency, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) have emerged as promising tools for automating forestry maintenance tasks, particularly branch pruning [2]. UAVs eliminate the need for human climbers, thereby reducing workplace accidents while maintaining or improving pruning precision. Our research team has developed an autonomous drone system equipped with stereo cameras for branch detection and a specialized pruning mechanism capable of accurately trimming branches at various heights. This approach not only enhances worker safety but also increases pruning efficiency in commercial Radiata Pine plantations.

Accurate distance estimation to tree branches from stereo

camera-generated depth maps is crucial for successful UAV-assisted pruning operations. Previous research has explored integrating Semi-Global Block Matching (SGBM) [3] with segmentation models for branch detection and distance measurement in radiata pine forests [2]. Furthermore, combining stereo vision with You Only Look Once (YOLO)-based object detection [1] has shown promising results in precise branch localization, enhancing both identification and pruning efficiency.

While neural network-based approaches [4], such as Pyramid Stereo Matching Network (PSMNet) [5], provide high-precision depth estimation, their significant computational demands result in low frame rates (approximately 1 second per frame), making them impractical for real-time UAV applications. In contrast, the traditional SGBM method [6] generates depth maps more rapidly (approximately 0.5 seconds per frame) but requires meticulous parameter tuning to balance speed and accuracy. SGBM also offers superior interpretability compared to neural networks through its transparent pixel-wise matching and structured cost aggregation processes—a critical advantage for safety-critical UAV operations where understanding algorithm behavior is essential. This structured methodology makes SGBM particularly suitable for UAV systems with limited computational resources.

Despite SGBM's advantages, its performance heavily depends on parameters traditionally tuned manually based on experience. To overcome this limitation, we propose a Genetic Algorithm (GA) [7] framework to optimize SGBM and Weighted Least Squares (WLS) [8] that systematically adjusts key parameters to enhance depth map accuracy while maintaining computational efficiency. GA is particularly well-suited for this task because it excels in global search for complex, high-dimensional optimization, efficiently exploring a large parameter space and avoiding local minima [7]. By iteratively refining candidate solutions, our GA approach ensures systematic parameter optimization, achieving swift convergence while balancing accuracy and computational cost.

The **primary objectives** of this research are to: (1) develop an automated parameter optimization framework for SGBM+WLS that eliminates the need for manual parameter tuning; (2) improve the accuracy of disparity maps for tree branch detection while maintaining processing efficiency at 0.5 seconds per frame; and (3) validate the effectiveness of

GA in optimizing stereo matching algorithms.

Our experimental results demonstrate that the proposed GA-optimized SGBM and WLS framework significantly reduces the error between generated disparity maps and gold standard. This is evidenced by enhanced evaluation metrics: a 42.86% lower Mean Squared Error (MSE) [9] indicates reduced differences between estimated and true depth values, while higher Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) [9] and SSIM values (increases of 8.47% and 28.52%, respectively) reflect improved structural consistency and more effective perceptual detail capture [9]. Moreover, our method maintains high accuracy under varying lighting conditions and complex backgrounds, underscoring its robustness for UAV applications.

The key contributions of this work include:

- A novel GA-based optimization framework for automatically tuning SGBM and WLS parameters that eliminates the need for manual configuration;
- A comprehensive evaluation methodology using multiple image quality metrics (MSE, PSNR, SSIM) to assess disparity map quality;
- Empirical evidence demonstrating that GA-optimized parameters significantly outperform manually tuned configurations, particularly when dealing with varied imaging conditions; and
- A practical solution for resource-constrained UAV systems that achieves a balance between processing speed and depth estimation accuracy for UAV branch pruning applications.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Stereo Matching

Stereo matching [10] estimates depth by finding corresponding points in images from different viewpoints, generating disparity maps transformable into depth maps. Disparity estimation precision directly impacts depth measurement accuracy, crucial for UAVs balancing accuracy and processing speed.

Traditional methods range from simple Block Matching (BM) [11] using Sum of Absolute Differences (SAD) [3] or Sum of Squared Differences (SSD) [10] to advanced deep learning like PSMNet [5] and RAFT-Stereo [12]. Fig. 1 shows a typical pipeline. While neural networks offer higher accuracy, their processing times (over 1s/frame) are prohibitive for real-time UAVs, unlike optimized traditional methods (approx. 0.5s/frame).

The disparity-depth relationship [13] is:

$$Z = \frac{f \cdot B}{d} \quad (1)$$

where Z is depth, f focal length, B baseline, and d disparity. Small disparity errors cause large depth errors, especially for distant objects. Our approach uses deep learning outputs as benchmarks to optimize SGBM parameters, balancing accuracy and efficiency for UAV operations.

B. Semi-Global Block Matching and Weighted Least Squares for Disparity Map Generation

SGBM [3], an extension of Semi-Global Matching (SGM) [14], incorporates block-based matching and approximates

Fig. 1: Flowchart of traditional disparity map generation process.

global optimization via multi-directional cost aggregation, balancing efficiency and accuracy.

SGBM steps: (1) Compute initial matching costs using block-based intensity differences. (2) Aggregate costs along multiple paths for smoothness. (3) Select optimal disparities (minimum aggregated cost). (4) Post-process (sub-pixel interpolation, consistency checks, outlier removal). We further apply WLS filtering to preserve edges and smooth homogeneous regions. Fig. 2 illustrates this pipeline.

The SGBM energy function is:

$$E(D) = \sum_p C(p, d_p) + \sum_{p, q \in N(p)} P(d_p, d_q) \quad (2)$$

where $C(p, d_p)$ is the matching cost, usually measured by intensity or feature differences, and $P(d_p, d_q)$ penalizes disparity differences.

Cost aggregation along path r :

$$L_r(p, d) = C(p, d) + \min \begin{cases} L_r(p-r, d) \\ L_r(p-r, d \pm 1) + \alpha \\ \min_k L_r(p-r, k) + \beta \\ - \min_k L_r(p-r, k) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

WLS refinement:

$$E_{WLS}(D) = \sum_p (D(p) - \tilde{D}(p))^2 + \lambda \sum_{(p, q) \in N} w_{pq} (D(p) - D(q))^2 \quad (4)$$

where \tilde{D} is the initial disparity map, λ regularization strength, and w_{pq} edge-aware weights.

The pipeline starts with preprocessing (grayscale conversion, Sobel filter). Birchfield-Tomasi matching cost for pixel $p = (x, y)$ and disparity d (with $q = (x - d, y)$):

$$I_{\max}(p, d) = \max\{I_r(q-1), I_r(q), I_r(q+1)\} \quad (5)$$

$$I_{\min}(p, d) = \min\{I_r(q-1), I_r(q), I_r(q+1)\} \quad (6)$$

$$C_{\text{gray}}(p, d) = \max\{0, I_l(p) - I_{\max}(p, d), I_{\min}(p, d) - I_l(p)\} \quad (7)$$

Gradient costs (G_l, G_r are gradient magnitudes):

$$G_{\max}(p, d) = \max\{G_r(q-1), G_r(q), G_r(q+1)\} \quad (8)$$

$$G_{\min}(p, d) = \min\{G_r(q-1), G_r(q), G_r(q+1)\} \quad (9)$$

$$C_{\text{grad}}(p, d) = \max\left\{0, G_l(p) - G_{\max}(p, d), G_{\min}(p, d) - G_l(p)\right\} \quad (10)$$

Combined cost:

$$C(p, d) = \frac{(100 - \eta)C_{\text{gray}}(p, d) + \eta C_{\text{grad}}(p, d)}{100}, \quad 1 \leq \eta \leq 100 \quad (11)$$

Fig. 2: SGBM and WLS processing pipeline for disparity map generation.

SGM [14] aggregates costs along multiple paths r (Eq. 3). Aggregated cost: $S(p, d) = \sum_r L_r(p, d)$. Initial disparity: $d^*(p) = \arg \min_d S(p, d)$. Sub-pixel refinement:

$$d_{\text{sub}}(p) = d^*(p) + \frac{S(d^* - 1) - S(d^* + 1)}{2[S(d^* - 1) + S(d^* + 1) - 2S(d^*)]} \quad (12)$$

Post-processing: Uniqueness check ($S_2 - S_1 \geq \frac{\gamma}{100} S_1$), left-right consistency ($|D_L(x, y) - D_R(x - D_L(x, y), y)| \leq \Delta$), speckle filtering ($|R| < W \wedge \max_{p, q \in R} |D_L(p) - D_L(q)| \leq \delta$). WLS refinement (Eq. 4) uses edge-aware weights $w_{pq} = \exp\left(-\frac{\|I(p) - I(q)\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)$. GA-optimized SGBM and WLS provide accurate, efficient disparity estimation for UAVs.

C. Genetic Algorithms for Parameter Optimization

GAs [15], inspired by natural selection, are powerful optimizers, widely used in scheduling [16], machine learning [15], and multi-objective optimization [17]. They are effective for optimizing stereo vision algorithm parameters.

GA's main advantage is effectively exploring complex, non-linear parameter spaces. Traditional SGBM/WLS parameter tuning is manual, time-consuming, and often suboptimal. GA systematically evaluates parameter combinations to maximize disparity map quality.

The GA process have several steps: initialization (candidate parameter sets), fitness evaluation (MSE [9], PSNR [9], SSIM [18]), selection, crossover, and mutation. This automates SGBM/WLS parameter optimization, finding configurations outperforming manual tuning, especially against high-quality gold standard from RAFT-Stereo with NeRF-Supervision.

III. THE PROPOSED METHOD

Despite its efficiency, traditional SGBM implementations face significant challenges in parameter selection, which directly impacts disparity map quality. Recognizing these limitations, we leverage advanced optimization techniques to overcome these challenges. In this study, we employ GA [19] to automatically tune the SGBM parameters, thereby enhancing the accuracy of disparity map estimation. Furthermore, we apply WLS filtering [20] to improve the smoothness and reliability of depth estimates, as parameter choices significantly impact the resulting disparity maps.

In this section, we detail the key parameters of SGBM and WLS, and describe the encoding process used for their optimization. We also outline the methodology for employing a GA to search for the optimal parameter configuration.

TABLE I: Summary of Parameters for SGBM and WLS Optimization

Parameter	Description	Valid Range
α	Small smoothness penalty	$1 \leq \alpha \leq 99999$
β	Large smoothness penalty	$\alpha < \beta \leq 199998$
Δ	LR consistency threshold	$1 \leq \Delta \leq 100$
η	Gradient-intensity weight	$1 \leq \eta \leq 100$
γ	Uniqueness ratio	$1 \leq \gamma \leq 100$
W	Speckle window size	$1 \leq W \leq 1000$
δ	Speckle range	$1 \leq \delta \leq 1000$
λ	WLS regularization	$1 \leq \lambda \leq 99999$
σ	WLS edge sensitivity	$0 \leq \sigma \leq 0.99$ (step 0.01)

The evaluation of these optimized parameters is presented in Section IV.

A. Parameters of SGBM and WLS

Our stereo disparity estimation method combines the SGBM [3] approach with a WLS filter [8] to produce a refined disparity map. As demonstrated in the preceding mathematical formulations, the quality of the resulting disparity map is highly sensitive to multiple parameter settings that control different aspects of the stereo matching pipeline. These parameters directly influence the energy terms in Equations (2), (3), and (4), creating a complex parameter space with interdependent effects on disparity estimation accuracy.

The smoothness penalties α and β in Equation (3) critically determine how disparity discontinuities are handled during cost aggregation. The small penalty α leads to minor disparity changes (typically at slanted surfaces), while larger penalty β affects significant disparity jumps (usually at object boundaries). Optimizing the relationship between these penalties directly impacts the preservation of depth discontinuities and smoothness of homogeneous regions. Similarly, the gradient-intensity weight η balances the contribution of intensity-based and gradient-based matching costs, affecting the algorithm's robustness to illumination variations while preserving structural details.

Post-processing parameters including the left-right consistency threshold Δ , uniqueness ratio γ , and speckle filtering parameters (W and δ) govern the detection and handling of occlusions, ambiguous matches, and noise. Finally, the WLS parameters λ and σ control the edge-preserving smoothing operation described in Equation (4), with λ determining regularization strength and σ adjusting edge sensitivity.

Table I summarizes these nine critical parameters along with their valid ranges. Each parameter changes within specific constraints and interacts with other parameters in complex, nonlinear ways that are difficult to model analytically. This complexity makes manual parameter tuning exceptionally challenging and motivates our GA-based optimization approach as described in the following section.

B. Parameter Encoding for GA Optimization

In the previous subsection, we introduced the key parameters governing the SGBM and WLS algorithms, outlining their definitions and valid value ranges. In this section, we describe how a GA is utilized to optimize these parameters. It is important to note that even minor adjustments to these parameters

Fig. 3: Parameter encoding example for GA optimization of SGBM and WLS parameters, which is a 28-bit integer vector.

within the SGBM and WLS frameworks can substantially impact the quality of the resulting disparity map.

To optimize the nine parameters using a GA, each is encoded as an integer variable with a range from 1 to 10 in Table I. 28 integer variables, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_8 are used to represent the nine parameters. Each parameter is represented by one or more of these integer variables. For example, since the range of α is $1 \leq \alpha \leq 99999$, it is computed using five integer genes, x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4 , and x_5 , as follows:

$$\alpha = \text{int}\left((x_1 - 1) \times 10000 + (x_2 - 1) \times 1000 + (x_3 - 1) \times 100 + (x_4 - 1) \times 10 + x_5\right), \quad (13)$$

where $x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5 \in [1, 10]$. Similarly, other parameters are encoded using their respective variables: β uses x_6 through x_{10} , Δ uses x_{11} and x_{12} , η uses x_{13} and x_{14} , γ uses x_{15} and x_{16} , W uses x_{17} through x_{19} , δ uses x_{20} through x_{22} , λ uses x_{23} through x_{27} , and σ uses x_{28} .

In the GA method, a 28-bit vector is used to represent the nine parameters in the SGBM and WLS algorithms as chromosome. Each bit ranges from 1 to 10. This encoding ensures a uniform representation of the entire search space, as illustrated in Fig. 3.

Based on the above encoding/representation method, GA utilizes a custom two-point crossover operator that randomly selects two crossover points along the chromosome and exchanges the segment between them from two parent individuals. This operation effectively combines advantages from both parents while ensuring that all gene values remain within the prescribed integer bounds—each gene is rounded and constrained within the range $[1, 10]$.

To further enhance exploration of the parameter space and prevent premature convergence, a uniform integer mutation operator is applied. With a mutation probability of 0.3 for each gene, any mutated gene is replaced by a new integer randomly chosen from the range $[1, 10]$. This mechanism introduces the necessary randomness to maintain genetic diversity across the population.

Following the generation of offspring through crossover and mutation, an elitist selection strategy is employed. Specifically, the top five individuals, based on their fitness scores, are retained for the next generation.

C. Fitness Evaluation

For fitness evaluation within our GA framework, we employ three different image quality metrics: MSE [9], PSNR [9], and SSIM [18]. Each metric served as an independent fitness function, which forms three variants of the proposed GA method. Allowing us to analyze how different evaluation criteria influence parameter selection and resulting disparity map characteristics.

Fig. 4: Crossover, mutation, and environment selection in GA.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (D_{GT}(i) - D_{SGBM+WLS}(i))^2 \quad (14)$$

MSE quantifies pixel-level accuracy by measuring the squared difference between corresponding pixels in the ground truth disparity map (D_{GT}) and our SGBM+WLS generated disparity map ($D_{SGBM+WLS}$). As a fitness function, it drives the GA search toward parameter sets that minimize overall numerical error. The squaring operation makes MSE particularly sensitive to large disparities, encouraging the identification of parameters that avoid significant depth estimation errors critical for collision avoidance in UAV navigation. However, MSE treats all pixels with equal importance regardless of their visual significance or structural context.

$$PSNR = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{d_{\max}^2}{MSE} \right) \quad (15)$$

PSNR expresses quality on a logarithmic scale relative to the maximum possible disparity value (d_{\max}). When used as a fitness function, it tends to produce parameter configurations that achieve more balanced error distributions across the disparity map. The decibel (dB) scale provides intuitive interpretation, with higher values indicating better quality and each 6dB increase approximately corresponding to a doubling of signal quality. PSNR-guided optimization typically results in parameters that produce more consistent depth representation across the entire image, with particular improvements in homogeneous regions.

$$SSIM(D_{GT}, D_{SGBM+WLS}) = \frac{(2\mu_{GT}\mu_{SGBM+WLS} + C_1)(2\sigma_{GT, SGBM+WLS} + C_2)}{(\mu_{GT}^2 + \mu_{SGBM+WLS}^2 + C_1)(\sigma_{GT}^2 + \sigma_{SGBM+WLS}^2 + C_2)} \quad (16)$$

SSIM evaluates structural similarity rather than pixel-wise differences, incorporating luminance (μ), contrast (σ), and structure ($\sigma_{GT, SGBM+WLS}$) components. This perceptually aligned metric ranges from -1 to 1, with 1 indicating perfect structural similarity. When employed as a fitness function, SSIM guides the GA toward parameter configurations that

Fig. 5: Left and right stereo image pairs captured using a ZED Mini camera mounted on a UAV in a Radiata Pine forest environment. Blue markings indicate UAV pruning tools, red markings highlight tree branches, and orange markings identify tree trunks.

preserve edge structures and textural patterns, particularly important for maintaining the integrity of tree branch boundaries and depth discontinuities. Our experimental analysis showed that while MSE optimization minimized overall error, PSNR balanced signal quality with region consistency, and SSIM best preserved structural fidelity—making SSIM-optimized parameters most suitable for UAV pruning, as detailed in Section V.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

This section systematically evaluates our GA-based parameter optimization for SGBM and WLS, detailing gold standard disparity acquisition, metric-based analysis, and comparisons with manual tuning to demonstrate robustness and generalizability.

A. Gold standard Acquisition using NeRF-Supervised RAFT-Stereo

We created high-quality disparity maps using NeRF-Supervised [21] RAFT-Stereo [12] as gold standard for evaluation. A ZED Mini stereo camera mounted on a UAV captured 654 high-definition (1920×1080) RGB stereo image pairs of Radiata Pine branches under consistent lighting conditions. Gold standard disparity maps were generated by training RAFT-Stereo on KITTI2012 [22] and KITTI2015 [23] datasets, fine-tuning on our forestry dataset, and refining with NeRF-Supervised loss. This yielded detailed disparity maps accurately delineating tree branch structures. For systematic evaluation, we selected two representative test cases—Examples 33 and 474—containing varying branch structures and imaging conditions. Fig. 5 presents the original left and right RGB images of these examples, while Fig. 6 displays their corresponding gold standard disparity maps.

B. GA-Based Parameter Optimization

We applied our GA framework to Example 33 with parameters shown in Table II. We used 30 population size and 100 generations to balance exploration and efficiency, with crossover and mutation probabilities of 0.6 and 0.3 respectively. To ensure

Fig. 6: Reference disparity maps generated using RAFT-Stereo with NeRF-Supervised training for quantitative evaluation.

TABLE II: Parameters of the GA Optimizer

Parameter Name	Value	Parameter Name	Value
Population size	30	Crossover probability	0.6
Chromosome length	28	Mutation probability	0.3
Number of generations	100	Retain top chromosomes	5

statistical validity, we conducted 30 independent runs for each fitness function (MSE, PSNR, SSIM), mitigating GA’s stochastic nature and providing robust performance assessment.

C. Quantitative Performance Analysis

Fig. 7 illustrates the progression of our three evaluation metrics across 100 generations of GA optimization for Example 33. The plots demonstrate clear convergence patterns for all metrics, with substantial improvements during the first 40 generations followed by more gradual refinements. Analyzing

Fig. 7: Evolution of evaluation metrics during GA optimization for Example 33. Each plot shows average performance over the 30 independent runs, with shaded regions indicating standard deviation.

convergence trends in Fig. 7, MSE exhibits rapid initial improvement (75% reduction in first 30 generations), PSNR shows steep initial improvement then incremental gains, while SSIM demonstrates consistent improvement throughout. Narrowing standard deviation bands confirm GA robustness across 30 independent runs. Quantitatively, GA-optimized parameters achieved 42.86% MSE reduction, 8.47% PSNR increase, and 28.52% SSIM improvement compared to baseline. The substantial SSIM improvement is particularly significant as it better captures structural integrity of branch features critical for UAV pruning. Parameter configurations optimized for one metric generally improve others, indicating alignment between quality aspects while confirming each metric emphasizes different disparity map characteristics.

Fig. 8: Comparison of disparity maps for Example 33 generated by SGBM+WLS using manually configured and GA-optimized parameters.

Fig. 9: Disparity maps for Example 474 generated using manually configured and GA-optimized parameters (transferred from Example 33), demonstrating superior generalization capability of GA-optimized parameters.

D. Comparative Analysis on Disparity Map Quality

We compared disparity maps from GA-optimized versus manually tuned parameters (Fig. 8). While GA parameters achieved superior quantitative metrics, manual parameters sometimes yielded clearer branch delineation, highlighting that global optimization metrics may compromise fine details in specific regions. To evaluate generalizability, we applied both parameter sets from Example 33 to Example 474 with different imaging conditions. As shown in Fig. 9, manual parameters performed poorly while GA-optimized parameters maintained consistent performance.

This result highlights a critical advantage of our GA-optimization approach: while manually tuned parameters may achieve good results for specific images, they often fail to generalize across varied imaging conditions. In contrast, our GA-optimized parameters demonstrated superior adaptability, producing structurally coherent disparity maps across different examples with varying image characteristics. Our results demonstrate that GA-based parameter optimization effectively improves SGBM+WLS disparity map quality across multiple metrics, with superior generalization across varied imaging conditions—crucial for dynamic UAV applications.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a GA-based parameter optimization approach for SGBM+WLS stereo matching in UAV applications. Our method systematically explores parameter space, achieving 42.86% MSE reduction, 8.47% PSNR increase, and 28.52% SSIM improvement compared to baseline configurations. GA-optimized parameters demonstrate superior adaptability across varied imaging conditions compared to manual tuning. While processing at 0.5 seconds per frame (faster than neural networks but not real-time), optimization opportunities exist through C++ implementation, GPU acceleration, or parallel processing. For UAV pruning tasks, SSIM-

optimized parameters provide superior structural representation of branches critical for successful operations.

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